

insecticide (see table). The carbohydrate-nitrogen ratio in decamethrin-treated TN1 plants was lower than in the control and in Perthane-treated plants, and may

explain the enhanced feeding of BPH on decamethrin-treated plants. No marked changes in the levels of starch and soluble sugars were observed in the leaf sheath tissue of insecticide-treated

plants.

Biochemical changes after insecticide treatment in plants of the BPH-resistant IR36 were not as vivid as those in the TN1 plants. ■

The black beetle as a pest of rice in Haryana, India

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The grub stages of scarabaeid beetles have reportedly caused serious damage to a number of kharif crops other than paddy in different states of India. In the course of a 4-year field survey (1977-78 to 1980-81), the author observed the black beetle *Heteronychus lioderes*

Redt. (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae: Dynastinae) damaging both nursery and transplanted paddy crop from June to August. The fields had clay soil and were classed as irrigated fields. In these fields paddy-wheat crop rotation is followed. Earlier, some workers had observed this pest damaging nurseries in North India and Burma. In Haryana the pest was found damaging nurseries and transplanted rice for the first time.

The beetle cuts the stem from the base below the soil, leaving behind a thin layer of stem. The plant dries up within

a few days. At the start, the central leaf of the plant droops, a symptom that may be confused with stem borer damage. After feeding on one plant the pest migrates to others on the same hill and thus kills the entire hill. As many as three beetles per hill were found. It was observed that in plants close to field boundaries, the damage was greater than elsewhere. However, the level of attack was low and no economic damage to the crop was observed.

The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology identified the insects. ■

Nomenclatural changes for some rice insect pests

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Cnaphalocrocis medinalis (Guenee), rice leaf folder

Confusion exists among rice entomologists as to the correct spelling of the genus *Cnaphalocrocis* Lederer. In almost all literature pertaining to this pest the genus has been incorrectly spelled *Cnaphalocrosis*; the correct spelling is *Cnaphalocrocis* (Hampson 1896, Fauna of British India, Moths; Vane-Wright 1980, British Museum, personal communication).

Cofana spectra (Distant), white rice leafhopper

A series of nomenclatural changes has occurred with the white rice leafhopper belonging to the genus *Tettigella*. The species *spectra*, formerly under *Tettigella*, was transferred to *Cicadella* Latreille, because *Tettigella* erected by China and Fennah was a junior objective synonym of *Cicadella* (China and Fennah 1945, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. [11] 22:711). But in 1966, the International

Commission on Zoological Nomenclature suppressed *Cicadella* under the plenary powers citing the Laws of Priority and Homonymy (China and Doyle 1966, Official Index of Rejected and Invalid Generic Names in Zoology, 2nd installment: names 1170-1743, Opinion 647:171).

In a recent review of the leafhopper genus *Cofana* Melichar, *Cicadella*, *Tettigella*, and *Tettigoniella* became synonyms of *Cofana* (Young 1979, Proc. Entomol. Soc. Wash. 81[1]: 1-21). Therefore, *Cofana spectra* (Distant) is the correct name.

Cofana yasumatsui Young, small white rice leafhopper

In the review of *Kolla* Distant (1971, Trans. Shikoku Entomol. Soc. 11 [1]:18), Ishihara erected *Yasumatsuus* to accommodate *mimicus* and used *Kolla mimica* Distant as the type species. Thus, *Yusumatsuus mimitus* (Distant) became the valid name. But in the recent review of *Cofana* Melichar, *Yusumatsuus Ishihara* became a synonym of *Cofana*. The correct name is *Cofana yasumatsui* Young.

To differentiate by common name the two species of white rice leafhoppers, we propose small white rice leafhopper for *Cofana yasumatsui* (length of male 6.4-

7.5 mm, female 7.2-8.0 mm) and white rice leafhopper for *Cofana spectra* (length of male 8.0-8.6 mm, female 8.5-9.8 mm).

Tryporyza vs *Scirpophaga*, white and yellow rice stem borers

The use of scientific names for white and yellow rice stem borers has been inconsistent despite several taxonomic studies (I. F. B. Common, 1960, Aust. J. Zool., Melbourne 8[2]:307-347; A. Kapur, 1964, Taxonomy of Rice Stem Borers, p. 3-43, in The Major Insect Pests of the Rice Plant; A. D. Pawar, 1975, The Rice Entomology Newsletter 2:8). Personal communication with Dr. A. Lewvanich (Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 9, Thailand) stressed that the generic characters used by Dr. Common for *Tryporyza* were too narrowly defined to be of generic value. Dr. Lewvanich pointed out that Dr. Common failed to examine other *Scirpophaga* species occurring outside Australia. Therefore many overlapping characters exist that are impossible to restrict only to *Tryporyza*. We therefore recommend the use of *Scirpophaga innotata* (Walker) for white rice borer and *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) for yellow rice borer. ■